

Determinants of Factors and Conflicts on The Performance of Balinese Women as Bank Employees

Ni Ketut Sariani, Ketut Sudarmini & Nengah Ganawati

Abstract

Women who work as bank employees still often experience work family conflicts, so it is not uncommon for it to become a burden on the thinking of workers. In addition, real conflicts (especially time conflicts) greatly affect the performance of female bank employees, including at Bank BPD Bali. Conflict between work and family is one of the elements that may have an impact on how well female bank employees perform. Conflict between work and family frequently develops when one of the jobs at work is more demanding or requires more focus than the position at home. Work-life balance is a factor that can impact employee performance in addition to work-family conflict. In this study, social support will be tested and its effects on work-family conflict, work-life balance, and the performance of female bank workers will be examined. A questionnaire (the Likert Scale) that has undergone validity and reliability testing was used to gather the results. Meanwhile, the sample was determined by 80 people with incidental sampling techniques. Furthermore, the collected data were analyzed with SEM-PLS analysis techniques.

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Introduction

Performance is the end result of work that may be completed by an individual or group of individuals inside an organization, in line with their separate authority and duties, in order to legally, ethically, and morally fulfill the company's goals. Work-family conflict is one of the elements that might impact employee performance. In terms of economics, having a working married couple (a "two-worker family") improves the welfare of the family and society. Work-family conflict is the division between work and family that will have a negative impact on performance and family. Conflict between work and family frequently develops when one of the jobs at work is more demanding or requires more focus than the position at home. There is no denying that this dispute led to a number of issues that had an impact on the woman's familial and professional lives. On the one hand, women are expected to manage and raise their families in the right way, while on the other hand, as employees, let alone bank employees, women are expected to work to high performance standards. However, not all of them can balance job and family responsibilities, which causes work-family conflict (Minarika et al., 2020). Work-life balance is a factor that can impact employee performance in addition to work-family conflict. The balance between life at work is an important factor that needs to be considered by companies or organizations in making a policy so that work performance and productivity are maintained. Domestic activity has long been attached to women. The association of these two things even existed long before most women were born. It later became a culture and customs. The role of women is still traditionally addressed to non-economic activities, namely the role of women as caregivers and take care of the household, but in reality this is not the case. Along with the development of an increasingly complex society, the role of women has also shifted. In ancient times men played the role of breadwinners (public), while women lived at home taking care of domestic affairs. But today the times have changed. Not only men take part in the public sphere, but women have also played a role in economic and public activities. The participation of women in household economic activities is a common phenomenon that has been going on for a long time and reaches the entire socio-economic system of society (Tuwu, 2018). This research will photograph female bank employees, especially those working at BPD Bali. Based on preliminary observations, it is known that female bank employees at Bank BPD Bali are very vulnerable to *work family conflicts*, because of job demands, such as frequent additional working hours / overtime, so it is not uncommon for it to be a burden on the thinking of female bank employees. In addition, real conflicts (especially time conflicts) greatly affect their performance. Women frequently have role tensions, particularly working women. The demands of the family frequently lead to subpar job output; conversely, the demands of the workplace can also disrupt family unity. The value of social support for one another is also present in the social life of the Balinese people, who are strongly attached to one another. Balinese women must be able to maintain a balance between their personal and professional lives. Where the balance is will also affect how well they perform. Thus, it is crucial to demonstrate and examine the role of society (as measured by social support), family (work-family conflict), and the individual (work-life balance) as well as their effects on the productivity of working women, in this case bank workers. The purpose of this study is to examine how social support affects female bank employees' performance, work-family conflict, and work-life balance. This study's focal point is PT. Bank BPD Bali.

Literature Review

The Concept of Social Support

Social Support is information in which the individual is loved, cared for, valuable. As well as part of a communication network that is the obligation of parents, spouses, family, friends which includes comfort, attention, appreciation or help that the individual gets from others. Others are defined as individual individuals or groups. For individuals who gain social support

will believe the individual is loved, cared for, valued from his social environment. When faced with a problem, individuals with a high level of social support will feel less stress and be able to coping well (Taylor, 2012; King, 2012). Social Support can come from life partners, family members, social and community contacts, group friends, and workmates (Taylor, 2012). Social Support is effective for overcoming psychological distress, reducing the psychological response to stress, and strengthening functions to strengthen functions to respond (King, 2012). Social support involves more than simply giving aid; it also involves how the receiver interprets what is being offered to them. This is directly tied to the social support that is given being accurate, which means that those who receive it actually experience the advantages of aid for themselves since it is something that is genuine and satisfying. Therefore, this variable is quite important to be studied to be applied to the family environment. There are six provisions that must be met in order for a person to feel adequately supported (Taylor, 2012). namely: First, Emotional Attachment; the presence of a feeling of emotional closeness to others that gives a sense of comfort. Second, Social Integration; refers to the feeling of having the same interests, concerns, and recreational activities. Individuals have the feeling of being part of a group, a place to share interests, attention as well as do fun activities together. Third, The Reassurance of Worth; the existence of recognition from others of the competencies, skills and values that the individual has. Employees are recognized for their abilities and expertise and are rewarded by others or institutions. Fourth, Reliable reliance; there is a belief that there are others who can be relied upon to help solve the problem. Fifth, Guidance; opportunity for nurturance. The sensation of needing others is a crucial element in interpersonal interactions, which brings us to the sixth opportunity for nurturing.

The Concept of Work Family Conflict

Some scholars refer to this situation as "work family conflict" to describe the ongoing challenges of being unemployed on persons with families (Siegel et al., 2005). When the energy, time, or conduct of job demands collide with family responsibilities, it results in work family conflict (Erkmen and Esen, 2014). When a person plays several roles, such as job and family, they may become incompatible with one another or experience an inter-role conflict when different demands apply to playing family and professional roles (Neto et al., 2016; Howard, 2008). Work Family Conflict is a key factor for many employees, (Wilson and Baumann, 2015). The use of the term Work Family Conflict has two forms, namely work-family conflict and family-work conflict (Yavas and Babakus, 2008). These factors are supported by the increasing number of women who feel the importance of their careers, how to want to maintain a lifestyle, and the desire to escape from poverty. Whereas on the other hand children or families often need more attention. This is coupled with the rise of gender equality activities and the 'necessity' of women or women to work which erodes the traditional view that women take care of the house and men who work. The tendency to go ahead to the balance of male and female roles is increasingly apparent. This condition is characteristic of the conflict that exists in every working family, where they are faced with equally severe choices (Neto et al., 2016; Howard, 2008). Conflicts between work and family life often occur due to insecurity in the values adopted. Therefore, values in the family and work are important so that there is a balance between work and family. So this research is important to see a good relationship between families, workers, and employers in overcoming conflict problems that often occur in work related to the family. According to Zhang et al. (2012), there are three (three) aspects of work-family conflict: First Time-based Conflict, which is when one of the demands (family or work) requires more time to complete than the other (work or family). Thirdly, behavior-based conflict, which is connected to the difference between the pattern of conduct and the intended part of both parts (work/family), happens when the pressure of one role impacts the performance of the role of the other. There are 5 (five) factors that affect Work-Family Conflict

(Zhang et al., 2012), namely: (1) Pressure as a parent, (2) Marital Pressure, (3) Lack of involvement as a couple, (4) Lack of parental involvement, and (5) Work interference. The issue of work-family conflict is frequently viewed as a possible cause of stress that may have a detrimental impact on employee behavior and well-being (Amstad et al., 2011). According to recent research (Dugan et al., 2012), upgrading work-family conflict assessments should focus on subjective factors like working hours or the experience of time pressure.

The Concept of Work Life Balance

The ability to strike a balance between the demands of work and one's personal and family life is known as "work-life balance" (Schermerhon, 2005). Work-life balance is the point where a person's personal and professional lives are equally balanced, according to Clarke et al. (2004). Personality, wellbeing, and emotional intelligence are internal elements that affect work-life balance, whereas norms, or factors originating from companies and the social environment, are examples of external players. According to Ramadhani and Hendrasti (2013), there are three components of measuring work-life balance, namely time balance, engagement balance, and satisfaction balance.

The Concept of Performance

Performance is the outcome of labor that a person or group of individuals in an organization may complete in line with their separate authority and duties, in order to lawfully accomplish the company's objectives while abiding by morals and ethical principles (Minarika et al., 2020). According to Hasibuan (2010), performance is the end result of a person's labor in completing the duties assigned to him and is dependent on skill, experience, sincerity, and time. Mangkunegara (2012) added that reliability, dependability of a person's job, quality of work, and attitude may all be used to gauge performance.

Previous Research

The association between social support factors, work-family conflict, work-life balance, and performance has already been the subject of a number of research. The female workforce is the subject of certain research. This is so because women are more likely to experience role conflicts in a place like Indonesia. According to Minarika et al. (2020), the study's findings show a very substantial correlation between employee performance and both work-family conflict and work-life balance (study at PT. Pacific Eastern Coconut Main Pangandaran). The hypothesis is accepted, which means that there is a beneficial impact of work-family conflict and work-life balance on employee performance, according to the findings of the hypothesis test. Therefore, employee performance will rise to a greater extent when work-family conflict and work-life balance are better maintained. This concurs with Singh and Khanna's (2011) assertion that "work-life balance" is a broad concept that entails establishing the proper priorities between work (career and ambition) and life (happiness, leisure, family, and spiritual development) on the one hand and in order to increase employee performance and job satisfaction. Life happiness will rise due to social support and the low work-family conflict that exists. Consequently, social support and work-family conflict have an impact on subjective wellbeing (Nguyen et al., 2016; Monfared et al., 2017). Workload has a significant negative impact on work-life balance, work-family conflict has a significant negative impact on work-life balance, workload has no direct impact on life satisfaction, work-family conflict has no direct impact on life satisfaction, work-life balance has a positive impact on life satisfaction, and workload has a significant negative impact on life satisfaction through work-life balance, according to research by Halim and Heryjanto (2021).

Research Framework

Based on *the literature review* and review of the results of previous research, a conceptual framework for research can be compiled as Figure 1.

Figure 1.: Research Conceptual Framework

Method

Mudjiyanto (2018) explained that several experts explained that there are three types of research, namely exploratory research (aimed at exploring), descriptive (aimed at describing), and explanatory (aiming at testing). Given that this study is to test, this research can be categorized as explanatory research. Furthermore, the operationalization of research variables can be compiled as presented in

Table 1: Operationalization of Research Variables

Not.	Variable	Definition	Indicators
1.	Social support (X)	Iam informed of which the individual is loved, cared for, valuable.	Emotional closeness / emotional attachment (X1)
			Integratation of social / social harmony (X2)
			The existence of recognition / reanssurence of worth (X3)
			Reliable reliance (X4)
			Guidance (X5)
			Opportunity for nurturance (X6)
2.	Working Family Conflict (Y1)	Bforms of conflict between roles that occur when energy, time, or work-demanding behavior conflicts with family roles.	Time-based conflict (Y11)
			Strain-based conflict (Y12)
			Behavior-based conflict (Y13)
3.	Work Life Balance (Y2)	A person's ability to balance between the demands of work and his personal and family life.	Time balance (Y21)
			Balance of engagement (Y22)
			Satisfaction balance (Y23)
4.	Performance (Y3)	Hasil work that a person achieves in carrying out the duties charged to him which is based on ats proficiency, experience and earnestness and time.	Working quality (Y31)
			Working quantity (Y32)
			Reliability (Y33)
			Attitude (Y34)

Sources: Erkmen and Esen (2014), Zhang et al. (2012), Schermerhon et al. (2005), Ramadhani and Hendrasti (2005), Minarika et al. (2020), Nazwirman et al. (2018)

By gathering information from female business owners at PT Bank BPD Bali in Denpasar, this study employed a type of primary data to create a population of married female employees. According to Ghozali (2004), the maximum likelihood estimate model's sample size for SEM is between 100 and 200 samples, or up to five times the number of indicators (5 x 16 indicators = 80 samples). Incidental sampling is used to carry out the sample procedure or sampling method. A questionnaire that has undergone validity and reliability testing and uses a Likert scale is used to collect the data. The

gathered information is then tallied and examined using SEM-PLS analytical methods (SmartPLS applications).

Results and Discussion

Description of Research Variables

To determine how respondents see each study variable collectively, a description of respondents' perceptions based on remarks on research questionnaires is crucial. The mean value of each respondent's overall perception item was used to summarize the respondent perceptions based on the proportion of respondents' responses to the research statement. According to Ferdinand (2013), the three-box technique criteria may be used to interpret a perception index. Additionally, Ferdinand (2013) provided the three-box approach requirements listed below: A terrible or low appreciation score is between 10 and 40 percent, an adequate or moderate score is between 41 and 70 percent, and an excellent or high score is between 71 and 100 percent.

Table 2.: Respondents' Perceptions of Research Variables

Variables/Indicators	Amount In %					Perception	Appreciation
	Respondent Assessment Rate						
	1	2	3	4	5		
Social Support (X)							
Emotional closeness / emotional attachment (X1)	10.00	22.50	21.25	36.25	10.00	62.75	Enough
Integration of social / social harmony (X2)	5.00	21.25	36.25	22.50	15.00	64.25	Enough
The existence of recognition / reassurance of worth (X3)	11.25	21.25	18.75	42.50	6.25	62.25	Enough
Reliable reliance (X4)	6.25	26.25	27.50	28.75	11.25	62.50	Enough
Guidance (X5)	10.00	20.00	22.50	37.50	10.00	63.50	Enough
Opportunity for nurturance (X6)	8.75	27.50	22.50	30.00	11.25	61.50	Enough
Average	8.54	23.13	24.79	32.92	10.63	62.79	Enough
Working Family Conflict (Y1)							
Time-based conflict (Y11)	13.75	36.25	26.25	15.00	8.75	53.75	Enough
Strain-based conflict (Y12)	11.25	47.50	30.00	7.50	3.75	49.00	Enough
Behavior-based conflict (Y13)	12.50	36.25	41.25	8.75	1.25	50.00	Enough
Average	12.50	40.00	32.50	10.42	4.58	50.92	Enough
Work Life Balance (Y2)							
Time balance (Y21)	3.75	10.00	31.25	40.00	15.00	70.50	Enough
Balance of engagement (Y22)	5.00	21.25	27.50	38.75	7.50	64.50	Enough
Satisfaction balance (Y23)	12.50	11.25	30.00	30.00	16.25	65.25	Enough
Average	7.08	14.17	29.58	36.25	12.92	66.75	Enough
Performance (Y3)							
Working quality (Y31)	6.25	11.25	28.75	37.50	16.25	69.25	Enough
Working quantity (Y32)	5.00	15.00	35.00	36.25	8.75	65.75	Enough
Reliability (Y33)	13.75	12.50	23.75	43.75	6.25	63.25	Enough
Attitude (Y34)	3.75	23.75	21.25	41.25	10.00	66.00	Enough
Average	7.19	15.63	27.19	39.69	10.31	66.06	Enough

The results of a descriptive analysis of the frequency of respondents' answers to each question item showed that respondents gave sufficient assessments of all indicator items, so that on average all research variables were also considered sufficient.

Measurement of Outer Model

If an indicator has a loading factor and AVE against the desired construct that are both over 0.6, it is considered to be valid (convergent validity).

Figure 5.2 displays the outcomes of the algorithm test that demonstrates outer loading.

Figure 2.: External Loading Indicator

Meanwhile, the complete convergent validity test results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3.: Convergent Validity Test Results

Indicators	Variable			
	Social Support (X1)	Working Family Conflicts (X2)	Work-Life Balance (Y1)	Performance (Y2)
Emotional closeness / emotional attachment (X1)	0.776			
Integration of social / social harmony (X2)	0.840			
The existence of recognition / reanssurence of worth (X3)	0.890			
Reliable reliance (X4)	0.839			
Guidance (X5)	0.904			
Opportunity for nurturance (X6)	0.914			
Time-based conflict (Y11)		0.828		
Strain-based conflict (Y12)		0.734		
Behavior-based conflict (Y13)		0.800		
Time balance (Y21)			0.776	
Balance of engagement (Y22)			0.892	
Satisfaction balance (Y23)			0.897	
Working quality (Y31)				0.881
Working quantity (Y32)				0.855
Reliability (Y33)				0.835
Attitude (Y34)				0.860
AVE	0.743	0.622	0.734	0.736

All research indicators have constructions over 0.6 with their constructs, as shown in Table 5.4. Similarly, if the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) score is higher than 0.5, all research

indicators are considered to be reliable. On the basis of cross-loading the measuring actuator with its concept, the discriminant validity measurement of the measurement model may be assessed. A comparison of the correlation between an indicator of one construct and the correlation between that indicator and another construct is shown in Table 5.5.

Table 4.: Discriminant Validity Test Results

Indicators	Variable			
	Social Support (X1)	Working Family Conflicts (X2)	Work-Life Balance (Y1)	Performance (Y2)
Emotional closeness/emotional attachment (X1)	0.776	-0.190	0.281	0.568
Integration of social/social harmony (X2)	0.840	-0.363	0.427	0.630
The existence of recognition / reassurance of worth (X3)	0.890	-0.236	0.277	0.718
Reliable reliance (X4)	0.839	-0.208	0.325	0.684
Guidance (X5)	0.904	-0.294	0.436	0.679
Opportunity for nurturance (X6)	0.914	-0.336	0.451	0.682
Time-based conflict (Y11)	-0.273	0.828	-0.793	-0.347
Strain-based conflict (Y12)	-0.279	0.734	-0.393	-0.340
Behavior-based conflict (Y13)	-0.193	0.800	-0.440	-0.222
Time balance (Y21)	0.277	-0.507	0.776	0.176
Balance of engagement (Y22)	0.495	-0.629	0.892	0.426
Satisfaction balance (Y23)	0.318	-0.730	0.897	0.485
Working quality (Y31)	0.576	-0.370	0.420	0.881
Working quantity (Y32)	0.731	-0.492	0.517	0.855
Reliability (Y33)	0.593	-0.188	0.202	0.835
Attitude (Y34)	0.703	-0.261	0.360	0.860

Table 4 demonstrates that the construct has a high discriminant validity by showing that the correlation of construct indicators is higher than the correlation of those indicators with other constructs. Composite Dependability evaluates a construct's reliability value, whereas Cronbach's Alpha measures the lower limit of a construct's reliability value (Chin and Gopal in Salisbury et al, 2002). If the results are close to 0.7 (such as 0.6), it is still acceptable in exploratory trait research, but the Cronbach's Alpha or Composite Reliability role of thumb value should be better than 0.7. (Hair et al, 2010). Table 5 contains the findings from the construct reliability test.

Table 5.: Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability

Variable	Alpha Cronbach	Composite Reliability
Social Support (X)	0.930	0.945
Working Family Conflict (Y1)	0.711	0.831
Work Life Balance (Y2)	0.822	0.892
Performance (Y3)	0.881	0.918

Table 5. shows *the values of Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability* of each construct are valued greater than 0.70 so it can be said that the gauges used in this study are reliable.

Evaluation of Inner Model

The structural model in PLS needs to be evaluated by using *R-squares* for dependent variables and their significance values based on *the t-values* on each *path*.

Table 6.: R-square value

Variable	R-square
Social Support (X)	
Working Family Conflict (Y1)	0,102
Work Life Balance (Y2)	0,587
Performance (Y3)	0,614

The work family conflict construct has an R-square value of 0.090, as seen in Table 6. This suggests that while the social support construct can account for 10.2% of the variability of the work-family conflict construct, the remaining 89.8% is explained by other factors. In addition, social support and work-family conflict account for 58.7% of the explanations for the work-life balance construct; the remaining 41.3 percent is explained by other factors. The construct of social support, work family conflict, and work-life balance accounts for 61.4 percent of the variability of the performance construct, whereas other factors account for the remaining 38.6 percent.

Based on R² in Table 6, it can be calculated Q² or *Stone Geiser Q-Square test*, namely:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q^2 &= 1 - \{(1 - 0.102) (1 - 0.587) (1 - 0.614)\} \\
 &= 1 - \{(0.898) (0.413) (0.386)\} \\
 &= 0.857
 \end{aligned}$$

Since the Q² computation yielded a result of 0.857, which is considered to have a high predictive prevalence, the resultant model is valuable for making predictions. The ratio of 0.857 indicates that the differences in the variables social support, work-family conflict, and loyalty can explain 85.7% of the variance in kin erja, while other factors outside the model may explain the remaining 12.3%. Analysis of the direct, indirect, and combined influences of study variables is required to determine the effect between variables. Table 7 displays the findings of the examination of the interaction between the research variables.

Table 7.: Path Coefficient

	Original Sample	Average Example	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P-value
Social support → Work family conflict (X → Y1)	-0.319	-0.328	0.116	2.764	0.006
Social support → Work life balance (X → Y2)	0.216	0.215	0.067	3.211	0.001
Social support → Performance (X → Y3)	0.704	0.703	0.089	7.932	0.000
Work family conflict → Work life balance (Y1 → Y2)	-0.669	-0.677	0.054	12.327	0.000
Work family conflict → Performance (Y1 → Y3)	-0.133	-0.136	0.101	1.314	0.189
Work life balance → Performance (Y2 → Y3)	0.048	0.044	0.078	0.614	0.539

Where: *) Non Sig (α = 0.05)

Table 8.: Indirect Effect Value

	Original Sample	Average Example	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P-value
Specific Indirect Effect					
Social support → Work family conflict → Work Life Balance (X → Y1 → Y2)	0.214	0.219	0.075	2.866	0.004
Social support → Work Life Balance → Performance (X → Y2 → Y3)	0.010	0.011	0.020	0.525	0.600
Work family conflict → Work Life Balance → Performance (Y1 → Y2 → Y3)	-0.032	-0.028	0.052	0.617	0.538
Social support → Work family conflict → Work Life Balance → Performance (X → Y1 → Y2 → Y3)	0.010	0.010	0.019	0.532	0.595
Social support → Work family conflict → Performance (X → Y1 → Y3)	0.042	0.043	0.038	1.111	0.267
Total Indirect Effect					
Social support → Work Life Balance (X → Y2)	0.214	0.219	0.075	2.866	0.004
Social support → Performance (X → Y3)	0.063	0.065	0.045	1.403	0.161
Work family conflict → Performance (Y1 → Y3)	-0.032	-0.028	0.052	0.617	0.538

Table 9.: Summary of Direct Influence, Indirect Influence, and Total Influence Between Research Variables

Independent Construct	Dependent Construct								
	Working Family Conflict (Y1)			Work Life Balance (Y2)			Performance (Y3)		
	DE	IDE	TE	DE	IDE	TE	DE	IDE	TE
Social Support (X)	-0.319		-0.319	0.216	0.214	0.430	0.704	0.063	0.767
Working Family Conflict (Y1)				-0.669		-0.669	-0.133	-0.032	-0.165
Work Life Balance (Y2)							0.048		0.048

Where: DE=Direct Effect; IDE=Indirect Effect; TE=Total Effect

Discussion

The results of the data analysis showed that social support had negative and significant influence on work family conflict experienced by female employees at PT. BPD Bali. This means that if there is an increase in social support, it will reduce work family conflict significantly, and vice versa. Social support very important for a woman in Bali, especially with married status and having children. Moreover, Bali is an area with a fairly large quantity of traditional activities, so it is prone to work family conflicts. This is in accordance with the results of previous research from Fadilla and Rozana (2020) which examined the effect of social support on family conflict work in police officers with married status. Further strengthened by the results of Ulfah's (2019) research related to the influence of job satisfaction and social support on dual roles. Several other studies also support this result, such as the research of Kossek et al. (2011) and Zakaria and Ismail (2017). It is also known that social support directly affects the work-life balance, which means that the higher the social support, the higher the work-life balance of female employees in PT. BPD Bali, and vice versa. This demonstrates how PLEW's dimension may be increased via social support (Personal Life Enhancement of Work). This dimension is concerned with how much a person's personal life may influence how well they perform at work. As an illustration, if a person is content in his personal life, this may also improve his disposition at work. The findings of Nurhabiba's (2020) study on social support for work-life balance in PT are consistent with this. Several other studies that also showed corresponding results were the research of Martadinata et al. (2020). Furthermore, the results of the analysis also show that social support has a positive and significant effect on the performance of female employees at PT. BPD Bali, where the better the social support, the more significantly improved performance will be followed. Social support in general is able to increase performance by motivating, improving the quality of reasoning, job satisfaction, lowering work pressures, increasing adaptability and psychological well-being. In addition to psychological, a healthy physique and productive stress management can also be improved by providing attention, information, and feedback in times of mental stress. The results of the analysis showed that work family conflict directly had a negative and significant effect on work-life balance, but it turned out to be insignificant to performance. This shows that even if it is a conflict, its effect on performance is not very significant. As we know that most female employees are in-office duty, with clear work procedures (SOPs) so as to minimize performance fluctuations. Indirectly, social support has a significant effect on work-life balance through work family conflict. This means that if you want to realize work-life balance, it can be done through minimization of work family conflict. The results of related studies are also shown from the research of Selvarajan et al. (2013) on social support and work family conflict: testing models of indirect influence.

Conclusion

Based on the study of the data, it can be said that social support has a direct impact on the poor and substantial work-life balance that female employees at PT. BPD Bali experience. The work-

life balance of female employees at PT. BPD Bali is positively and significantly impacted by direct or indirect social support (via work-family conflict). At PT. BPD Bali, female employees' performance is directly impacted by social support. However, indirect social support (through work family conflict and work-life balance), has an insignificant effect on the performance of female employees at PT. BPD Bali. The suggestions that can be given as a follow-up to the research results include: (1) Family and relatives as the core element, it is necessary to continue to provide social support for women who work, especially in pt. BPD Bali, considering that psychologically the support will greatly affect the psyche of employees. (2) The Company, in this case PT. BPD Bali should also take steps to minimize work family conflict and increase social support, such as carrying out family gatherings. Or strive so that female employees can manage work time, especially when it comes to carrying out overtime. (3) Further research should be directed towards efforts to increase social support, as this is very important in the dual roles played by women, especially married ones.

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